

**CONSILIERE EDUCAȚIONALĂ ȘI VOCAȚIONALĂ ANGAJAREA PERSOANELOR CU
DIZABILITĂȚI "INCLUZIUNEA ESTE BUNĂ PENTRU AFACEREA TA!"**

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**EDUCATIONAL AND VOCATIONAL COUNSELING EMPLOYMENT OF PEOPLE WITH
DISABILITIES "INCLUSIVE IS GOOD FOR YOUR BUSINESS!"**

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Abstract

Incluziunea eficientă presupune urmărirea unui parcurs de integrare a persoanelor cu dizabilități atât în școală, cât și mai târziu. Obiectivul prezentei lucrări este de a accentua importanța privirii de către angajatori a persoanelor cu dizabilități nu numai ca potențiali angajați în posturile din firma lor, dar și ca niște colegi egali și respectați.

Abstract

The idea of efficient inclusion consists of not only following a person's with disabilities path in education, but also following that same path through the professional life. The main objective of this paper is to highlight the importance of the employer's view on a person with disabilities not only as a potential job candidate, but also as a respected and equal colleague.

Cuvinte cheie: învățământ special, consiliere școlară și vocațională, cerințe educaționale speciale.

Keywords: special education, school and vocational counseling, special educational requirements.

The treatment and care of people with disabilities appeared a long time ago in human history. For example, at one point during the Renaissance, a revolutionary phenomenon from a scientific, ideological and artistic point of view, which took place between approximately 1300 and 1700, Queen Elizabeth ordered the Government to take care of the needy. Among these needy people, there were also the disabled people of that time, who finally had an institution where they could be hospitalized and assisted in the long term.

During the English Reformation between the 1700s and 1800s, the classification of disabilities began and, much more than that, the first special education initiatives for the visually impaired, the hearing impaired, and more. This side of the reform helped shape a path towards a world where people with disabilities were no longer seen as permanent "patients", but their integration into society was desired.

A disability is a physical or mental impairment that severely limits life activities (such as walking, reading, and communication) as well as essential body functions (immune system functions, cell growth, digestive system, bowel, bladder, neurological functions, cerebral, respiratory, circulatory, endocrine and reproductive).

For people with disabilities, limitations imposed by adverse contexts can be frequent and have a strong impact. The World Health Organization (WHO) characterizes these limitations as more than physical obstacles, but as factors in a person's environment that, by their absence or presence, disrupt functioning and accentuate disability.

These factors may include:

- an environment or physical space partially or totally inaccessible to the person concerned;
- lack of relevant technological means of assistance (assistance, adaptive and recovery devices);
- the general negative attitude of the collective in the context towards disabilities;
- the absence or rudimentary presence of services, systems and policies that encourage the participation of all people with a health condition in all areas of life.

In the United States, the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) outlines protections for qualified individuals with disabilities. Under the ADA, the term disability refers to any person who suffers from a physical or mental impairment that may result in a substantial limitation in one or more major life activities.

1. Disabilities in adults: The 6 barriers

Attitude is the starting point of many barriers that people with disabilities face. The attitude aspect refers to stereotypes and prejudices. Many view a person's disability as a tragic shortcoming instead of looking at things proactively.

By a proactive attitude we mean assuming a social responsibility to adapt disabled people to live a fulfilling life.

Communication barriers are common in people who have problems with hearing, speaking or understanding in general. For example, not many products have provisions for the visually impaired, such as a description in Braille. Alternatively, only a few people learn sign language which creates a significant communication barrier for many.

Physical barriers are everywhere. From the moment a disabled person steps out of their own home,

they are faced with many obstacles, from walking on the sidewalk to going down or upstairs.

Political barriers are due to a lack of awareness of disability. Politics has a duty to ensure enforceable laws that guarantee equal participation of all citizens, including those with disabilities. Also, where this aspect is difficult to apply, benefits must still be granted to guarantee decent living conditions.

Social barriers are also everywhere, and follow a person with a disability throughout life. These barriers relate to how people with disabilities grow, learn, work, live and age. For example, people with disabilities are less likely to graduate from high school, find work, or have a good income.

Transportation barriers make people with disabilities dependent on others for everyday things, either unable to drive or without access to convenient private or public transportation. This dependence on others hinders their ability to travel and therefore maintain a stable job.

2. Discrimination of disabled people at work

Discrimination is the unfair or prejudicial treatment of individuals and groups based on characteristics that, in the present case, are related to the spectrum of disabilities.

Discrimination in the workplace has a significant impact on the lives of many, causing some to quit their jobs, feel isolated or even be denied a job. Discrimination in the workplace is still a problem today. For example, more than a third (36%) of UK adults report experiencing discrimination at work.

Direct discrimination occurs in the workplace when a superior or colleague shows prejudice or unfair behavior towards an employee. Direct discrimination can include direct comments, work policies that target certain employees with disabilities, and/or smaller interactions that build a culture of discomfort in the workplace.

Indirect discrimination can occur when all employees are treated the same, but the treatment results in an inherent disadvantage. What constitutes direct and indirect disability discrimination may vary according to local regulations.

Some common examples of disability discrimination at the site of work may include:

- Exclusion of employees with disabilities from the discussion of promotion or other opportunities;
- Refusal to provide assistive technology such as ramps for wheelchairs or screen readers;
- Issuing negative comments or observations towards employees with disabilities;
- The request by the employer or colleagues of the medical history of disabled employees;
- Demotion of an employee after he becomes a disabled person;
- Exclusion from promotion of an employee on the grounds that a member of his family suffers from a disability;
- Influencing the hiring process for people with disabilities;
- Harassment of employees with disabilities.

3. Measures to prevent and combat discrimination against people with disabilities at work

Measures that employers can take to prevent and combat discrimination in the workplace include:

- eliminating or reducing the risks of discrimination based on disabilities;
- offering support to any person with disabilities;
- ensuring that all policies are consistent and consistent with zero tolerance for disability discrimination;
- clarifying to all those in the collective of employees and customers who use the services that discrimination based on disabilities is against the company's policy;
- training staff on recognizing disability-related discrimination and encouraging employees to report such behavior;
- recognizing and promoting the benefits of an inclusive and diverse workforce that does not exclude people with disabilities;

A key advantage of these methods is that they require no resources other than policy writing and in-house training, so they can be adopted by both large companies with complex networks and small companies with a limited number of employees.

4. Benefits of workplace inclusion and employment of disabled people

People with disabilities have diverse perspectives, experiences, abilities and talents. Evidence shows that people with disabilities have a positive attitude to work and that employing people with disabilities can increase productivity and morale in the workplace.

Research published in 2018 demonstrates that the benefits of employing people with disabilities extend throughout the organization or business.

Returning to one of the aspects above, it should be noted that discrimination against disabled people may become less likely to occur when the professional collective is a diverse one.

If employers support and choose, in recruitment, including for people with disabilities, their company can encounter certain benefits such as:

- Attracting a wider pool of talent for jobs at all levels
- Assembling a workforce that reflects more effectively with the client audience but also with the entire community
- recruiting staff who have more resilience and problem-solving skills, skills developed through dealing with their own disability
- bringing new skills to the organization
- improving employee morale by treating everyone fairly
- promoting commitment to equality.

The Parent of the Child with Special Educational Needs

Educational partner and trainer

Family education has in mind the building of skills, norms, values of life within the family and targets its members, encompassing a wider area than parental education. Duming, in the 1990s, 1994, defined family education as a complex of social activities carried out by parents, in the family space, aimed at children through the interventionists, and in the direction of parents, being parental training.

The specificity of the disabled child's family involves the role of the parent as a mediator between the special child, whose adaptation to interpersonal relationships is difficult, and the others, the belonging community, that is, strangers.

Often this mediation is done with a lot of subjectivity, so parents can overestimate inappropriate reactions from a stranger, misinterpret neutral gestures, can give the child a wrong perception of those around them, insist on the malice and hypocrisy of the people around them, by feeding him the belief that his deficiency is not accepted, that there is a lot of intolerance around him, I turn disability into disability by approaching social difficulties as a terminus, it prevents children from understanding and accepting all aspects related to their own disability precisely because they themselves did not accept the child's disability.

The role of the mediator takes on a major importance because the parents' reactions to the child's disability determine the child's reactions of accepting/approaching his disability.

The reactions of overprotection, acceptance, denial or rejection group parents into several categories, such as: balanced parents, exaggerated parents, indifferent parents, authoritarian (rigid) parents, inconsistent parents.

Parents of children with CES go through several phases of suffering until the moment of accepting the situation, which we mention next: anger, at oneself and at others, negotiation, with God or other higher powers and with oneself, depression, sadness and regret, fear and insecurity, but also acceptance, emotional detachment and the cessation of self-struggle as claimed by Elisabeth Kubler-Ross /Grief Cycle in material studied at <https://www.flickr.com/photos/journeytogenius/accessible> November 2019.

The family is the one that assumes responsibility for its members, society has the role of supporting it. The purpose of working with the family is to expand its competences through the conscious involvement of its intervention and responsibility.

Family engagement is essential because the family of the child with disabilities and/or other SEN will never be able to function or manage the situation on their own but need additional resources, information and support.

In the conditions of the inclusive school, the role of the parents as an educational partner involves several aspects, namely through direct participation in the life of the school, parents can exercise their influence on certain decision-making processes aimed at the educational course by imposing their point of view on the functioning of the school and have a concrete participation to the implementation of managerial functions in the school. Another aspect is the school's embrace of the idea of integration or inclusion, which also depends on the attitude of parents in relation to the child's educational problems, the absence or indifference of parents coming in opposition to this approach, not least the reluctant or distrustful position of parents regarding the life and educational development of a child with special educational needs (slower or faster changes) creates

difficulties, erroneous representations/mentality do not develop positive attitudes.

Trust is the foundation of the link between family and school, proper communication ensures a mutual exchange of trust, Gherhuț (2006) mentioned.

The partnership involves the exchange of information, good practices, experiences, and for this communication to work, it is necessary to train/develop good active listening skills, to know how to listen, to be able to create some premises for collaboration.

For a more solid support of the inclusive school, the members of the students' families must comply with a minimum of requirements such as providing up-to-date information on their child regarding the preparation of homework, the style and manner of learning at home, his interests and the way he reacts in various situations, concerns, preferences/non-preferences, to take part in every school activity and to be active in the process of promoting various practices of educational integration of special children at all levels of social life.

Specific behavioral structures are imposed in order to accept and encourage the integration of people with special needs in their communities, who have the responsibility to provide support to teachers in choosing realistic strategy systems regarding the development and education of children, both in school and outside it through the provision of important information that helps to develop and implement the individualized curriculum for the child, the involvement in decision-making regarding the child and the continuous habilitation/rehabilitation programs of the child's development.

It is very important to accept without resentment the possible limitations implied by the level and difficulty of their deficiencies, but also to be sincere partners in a dialogue and to be open without any reservations about the collaboration with the team made up of specialists who have the task of educating and to make possible the recovery of the children, keeping under observation the evolution that they have presented to the children in different contexts in which life can bring them and to maintain a close relationship with the rest of the parents in the help group and to ensure that the personal experiences that they -have been with their own children in the activities that took place within the family are shared, and last but not least to be aware of the vast advantages that the inclusive school offers to special children to ensure that they will attend classes.

The inclusive school and all teachers have the responsibility to create an environment accessible to families in which both they and the special child can integrate, by mobilizing every family in which there are children with special educational requirements to take part in the established educational and therapeutic program, respecting the rights and grievances of families to opt for when, how and how much they can take part in therapeutic activities, respectively their continuation at home, but also ensuring that the exchange of information about the child takes place constantly with the family.

An important role is the location of the resources related to the educational and recuperative-therapeutic program intended for students with special needs,

through which the parents' effort can be supported, informing the family about the activities suggested by the recuperative-therapeutic program and its customization at the request of the parents, as well as bringing information to the family regarding any update appearing in the program, but also receiving the suggestions and impressions brought by the family and using them in order to improve the programs dedicated to students with educational requirements.

The partnership has a special role in the operation of the inclusive school, because within them the students are the main beneficiaries of the collaboration through which certain difficult situations can be anticipated and prevented, they contribute to the development of the educational and social skills of parents and other community actors and offer services and support families, ensures the facilitation of the exchange of ideas between the parties, gives birth to innovative ideas and contributes to the solution of certain problems.

The whole partnership facilitates the connection between the child and the family, between the families, the school staff and the community through the opportunity to actively participate in the educational experiences of the students.

Working in a team allows all the people involved in the education/development of the child with special educational requirements to satisfy the student's needs by identifying the student's strengths, interests and needs as clearly/precisely as possible and using the collected information and conclusions following the observation of the student's behavior for the purpose of

individualizing the curriculum for it, but also the establishment of consensus regarding curriculum planning by correlating the general curriculum goals with the individualized goals established in the PEI.

Another advantage of teamwork is establishing consensus on the way and level of providing support services to the student by suggesting/recommending appropriate educational strategies/technologies, establishing the place where the support activity is carried out (in the classroom, in the resource room/offices), establishing other services available in the community.

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